

USING E DICTIONARIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

This article discusses the significance and advantages of using electronic dictionaries in teaching and learning foreign languages. The authors highlight how e-dictionaries, as a modern technological tool, facilitate rapid word search, provide pronunciation guides, offer usage examples in different contexts, and support the development of both passive and active vocabulary. The article reviews different types of electronic and printed dictionaries, explains criteria for vocabulary selection, and describes practical strategies for integrating e-dictionaries into classroom activities. Special emphasis is placed on their role in enhancing language skills, improving cross-cultural communication, and promoting learner autonomy. The findings suggest that electronic dictionaries are an essential resource for effective and interactive foreign language education in today's digital age.

Key words: electronic dictionaries, foreign language teaching, vocabulary acquisition, language learning technologies, classroom strategies, learner autonomy, cross-cultural communication.

In today's globalized world, knowing foreign languages is more important than ever. Learning a foreign language has created a great opportunity for personal, professional success, and broadening one's horizons. And at the same time, modern technologies are also having an impact in this regard. "Technology is nothing. What's important is that you have a faith in people, that they're basically good and smart, and if you give them tools, they'll do wonderful things with them." (Steve Jobs)

The role of electronic resources in the education system, particularly in learning foreign languages, is growing. Learning a language involves not only memorizing new words, but also understanding their correct usage, pronunciation, meaning in context, and grammatical structure. In this regard, electronic dictionaries are becoming a reliable assistant for language learners. The basic problem is the selection criteria of vocabulary. L.V. Scherba (Scherba 1974), I.V. Rakhmanov (Rakhmanov 1956), P.N. Denisov (1974, 1976, 1993), V.V. Morkovkin, Yu. Safyan (Denisov, Morkovkin & Safyan 1978), Bogachev G.F. (Bogachev, Lutsk, Morkovkin & Popov 2003), Nation P. (Nation, P. & Newton, J. 1997) and many other domestic and foreign linguists and methodologists dedicated their studies to this issue of research and established a clear set of requirements for the selection of vocabulary (Yusupova 2014, Kharisov&Kharisova 2014, Ashrapova & Yusupova 2015, Varlamova&Safiullina 2015). The main academic principle of vocabulary selection is linguistic and statistical analysis of lexical units from selected sources; the analysis of a text starts with ranking of lexemes according to the frequency of usage.

First of all, we need to understand what electronic dictionaries are and how they can help us. What is an electronic dictionary?

An electronic dictionary is a software or web platform that is used on devices such as computers, tablets, phones, and other devices to translate or explain words and phrases in text, audio, or visual format. They allow you to search for words in one or more languages, translate them, listen to pronunciation, and learn usage through examples. Intensification and improvement of the quality of foreign language teaching require not only basic or innovative technologies, but also the availability of the primary database language. Linguistic teaching manuals comprise textbooks, work books, tests, teachers book, but all of them are based on the primary and most important element of the framework - dictionaries, specialized and customized for the needs of the pupils/- students. The following dictionaries are used by the teachers and students at the practical classes of the English language: the New large English-Russian Dictionary by Apresyan Yu.D (Apresyan 2002) in three volumes comprised of 250 thousands entries; the revised edition of the large English-Russian Dictionary by Muller V.K. (Muller 1995) consisting of 66 thousands entries; among the e-dictionaries the preference is given to the new version of Andrey Pominovs ABBYY Lingvo 12, that includes 6 mil. entries on 6 European languages (www.lingvo.ru), and Multitran, that is an automatic online dictionary, one of the fullest part of which is English Russian part (www.multitran.ru). With the help of an electronic dictionary, the user can find any word in a matter of seconds. For example, when reading a text through a mobile application,

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you can immediately see its translation and explanation by clicking on an unknown word. This saves time and helps to continue the learning process without interruption. Process of words learning and transmission from passive vocabulary into active vocabulary is facilitated with the dictionary. Tasks based on dictionary usage can be performed not only individually, but also in pairs, or in groups, thereby the new material is reinforced. (Meara 1983, 1987) Many online dictionaries, such as the Oxford Learner's Dictionary or the Cambridge Dictionary, allow you to hear the pronunciation of each word in both British and American English. This is especially useful for those learning English. For example, the word "schedule" is pronounced "shed-yool" in British pronunciation, and "sked-jool" in American pronunciation – you can learn the difference by listening. While a regular dictionary only provides a translation of a word, electronic dictionaries provide examples of its use in context. For example, the word "run" means "to run," but the phrase "run a business" means "to do business." With the help of such examples, the learner can more easily understand the meanings of the word in different contexts. For example, programs like ABBYY Lingvo or Reverso provide translation services in over 20 languages. These platforms also allow you to see translations of the same word in different contexts. And also The words as still, conversely, while, however, thus, furthermore, as a result, to be more precise, and others are included within the text of the English-Tatar dictionary for learners. They express different logical relationships within the text: explanation, clarification, comparison, the expansion of the concept, the opposition, summing up. Thus a user is enabled to build a complete statement and to perform the correct translation (Arslanova 2003, Ayupova 2014). With this, it helps to increase vocabulary. Some electronic dictionaries allow users to create personal word lists and practice using flashcards. For example, in the Quizlet program, the user enters English words and their translations and reinforces them with tests and games. One of the tasks of the teacher is to show the students to use and work with a bilingual dictionary to develop the learning ability of a student. The following operations are to be demonstrated and practiced under the supervision of a teacher: search for words in alphabetical order; plural form of nouns; meanings of ambiguous words; same-rooted words; conversed words; collocations; idioms, etc. This aforementioned list shows what an important role in the study of foreign language skills is the creation and usage of the ERD or ETD for learners, especially in cross-cultural communication (Gilazetdinova 2014). The practical issues of creation of the bilingual Dictionary are based on the aforementioned theoretical issues.

Teaching English as a foreign language has to deal with the impact of electronic dictionaries on the process of study, and learners tend to apply them more often than printed versions. The operation on electronic equipment or access to the internet causes no difficulties for young generation of students. (Kamenskaya 2000).

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